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Modern Solutions to Improve the Effectiveness of Treating Oral Changes Caused by Psychotropic Drugs

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Abstract: *Burning mouth syndrome is a chronic condition characterized by orofacial pain, usually without associated oral mucosal or tongue lesions [10, 5]. In addition to burning mouth syndrome, there are many other terms (more than a dozen) that describe the actual pain. The most commonly used are glossalgia, glossodynia, and stomatalgia.*

The etiology of burning mouth syndrome remains unclear [2, 8, 10]. The causative agents of the occurrence of burning are local irritants (sharp edges of teeth, defects in dentures, galvanic phenomena in the presence of dissimilar metals) [9, 3]. It is believed that the pathology of the gastrointestinal tract plays a major role in the development of this disease [1, 8], and the allergic aspect [1, 4] and peripheral neuropathy [4] are of great importance. EN Dychko (1990) notes that the etiological factors of stomatalgia can be exogenous (stressful influences, infectious-allergic, medicinal, surgical interventions, local irritants) and endogenous (diseases of internal organs and systems) factors.

Key words: *psychotropic substances, oral changes, treatment principles*

Introduction: Psychological factors play an important role in both the onset and persistence of burning mouth syndrome [4, 6, 7, 9]. Burning mouth syndrome often occurs after emotional trauma, the death of a loved one or cancer, or personal or professional difficulties [12, 19]. Emotional disorders are often combined with burning mouth syndrome, and a number of authors [9, 4, 19] emphasize the leading role of psychological factors in the development of this pathology.

Mental disorders are an integral part of the clinical picture of burning mouth syndrome [8, 5]. The most characteristic are: anxiety, depression, hypochondria and sleep disorders [5, 1, 2, 4]. It has been found that 95% of patients with glossalgia experience significant changes in the emotional sphere, which are primarily manifested in the form of anxiety and depression [10, 7, 4]. Mental changes in

patients with burning mouth syndrome have a wide spectrum and range from minor ailments to severe mental disorders, which should be taken into account when conducting therapy [5].

Research methods and materials: Treatment of patients with burning mouth syndrome remains one of the most complex and urgent problems of modern dentistry and neurology [13]. According to many authors, therapy requires the complex use of therapeutic measures: drug therapy [3], physiotherapy, psychotherapy, reflexotherapy, hyperbaric oxygenation and hirudotherapy [3, 4, 9]. A number of studies have noted the high therapeutic effectiveness of the use of transcutaneous electrical neurostimulation [7, 3]. Physiotherapeutic procedures are widely used: massage of the collar zone and head, galvanization of the upper cervical sympathetic nodes, endonasal electrophoresis of novocaine [5]

However, according to the general consensus, the main role in the treatment of burning mouth syndrome is played by psychotropic medications and psychotherapeutic methods.

Psychopharmacotherapy in patients with burning mouth syndrome includes the use of antidepressants, neuroleptics, tranquilizers [3] and anticonvulsants [10]. The pathogenetic significance of psychopharmacotherapy is associated with the impact on factors that contribute to the development of burning mouth syndrome (primarily negative emotions) [10, 4].

Psychotropic drugs are included in all treatment regimens for burning mouth syndrome, but the drug combination varies. The most commonly used antidepressants are tricyclics and selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors [7, 4]. Since the effect of antidepressants can be stimulating or sedative, the differential selection of drugs requires a clear understanding of the clinical features of the depressive state (predominance of anxiety or depression, signs of psychomotor agitation or inhibition). Drugs with a sedative effect - amitriptyline, levonormetazepam, mianserin - are more indicated for excitable depression, while antidepressants with a stimulating effect - melipramine, amitriptyline, fluoxetine - are more indicated for depression with apathy [1].

The analgesic effect is independent of their antidepressant activity and can be observed at doses lower than those usually effective in depression. Increasing the dose of amitriptyline has been shown to not only increase analgesia but also increase side effects. Antidepressant doses should be limited by anticholinergic side effects (dry mouth, accommodation disorders, constipation, urinary retention) [2, 10].

Conclusions: The presence of senesto-hypochondriacal disorders requires the combination of antidepressants with neuroleptics [1]. The choice of neuroleptic is determined by the characteristics of the clinical picture. It should be borne in mind that aliphatic derivatives of phenothiazines (chlorpromazine, levomepromazine, propazine) and thioxanthene derivatives (chlorprothixene) have a very strong sedative effect; and piperazine derivatives of phenothiazines (trifluazine, etaperazine) and butyrophenone derivatives (haloperidol, trifluoperidol) have a stimulating component [2]. The use of atypical neuroleptics seems to be the most promising [2]. Unfortunately, taking neuroleptics is often accompanied by the development of undesirable side effects [11]. Drowsiness, moderate tachycardia, headache, and decreased attention are often observed [3]. In addition, typical neuroleptics can cause extrapyramidal disorders and lead to the development of delirium or depression [2].

There are many indications for the effective use of tranquilizers for the treatment of burning mouth syndrome [10, 9, 2, 6]. Tranquilizers normalize the functional state of subcortical (primarily limbic) and cortical structures involved in the formation of emotional reactions, and inhibit polysynaptic spinal

reflexes [36]. Tranquilizers, which have a universal effect on psychovegetative symptoms, improve the well-being of patients, stabilize and increase the compensatory reserves of the body [22].

The most important and promising group of tranquilizers includes benzodiazepine derivatives: chlordiazepoxide, diazepam, nitrazepam, oxazepam, phenazepam [19]. The choice of a tranquilizer and its dosage, distribution during the day are carried out depending on the specific tasks. It should be borne in mind that the most pronounced sedative effect has doses of diazepam and phenazepam; sleeping pills - nitrazepam, vegetotropic - diazepam and medazepam, activating - trioxazine, medazepam. However, the use of tranquilizers alone does not provide a complete reduction in psychopathological symptoms [3]. Adequate pathogenetic treatment involves their use in combination with antidepressants and neuroleptics.

It is not surprising that the prescription of psychotropic drugs is accompanied by many errors [2], as a result of which patients refuse to take them or finish the course prematurely. On the other hand, long-term use of benzodiazepines leads to the development of addiction and dependence [4]. To reduce the negative effects of psychopharmacotherapy, it is possible to reduce the dose of psychotropic drugs and supplement it with psychotherapy.

Properly prescribed psychopharmacotherapy increases the effectiveness of treatment of patients with burning mouth syndrome, helps to increase patient adherence to therapy, and strengthens the partnership between the doctor and the patient [29]. The absence of cardiotoxic and anticholinergic effects in antidepressants from the group of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors makes them the first choice drugs in patients with somatic pathology [5]. It is important that the use of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors helps to improve the safety of prescribing antidepressants in elderly patients [2]. Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors and "dual-acting" antidepressants have allowed to raise the level of treatment of emotional and pain disorders in neurological practice.

Thus, psychotropic drugs for burning mouth syndrome can be considered as pathogenetic therapy. Rational implementation of psychopharmacotherapy allows to improve the well-being of patients.

Psychotherapy, like psychopharmacotherapy, is an integral part of therapeutic programs for patients with burning mouth syndrome. The clinical effectiveness of psychotherapeutic methods for burning mouth syndrome has been investigated on the basis of meta-analyses and literature reviews. According to a number of authors [1], a course of psychotherapeutic treatment consisting of hypnotherapy and autogenic training is effective for burning mouth syndrome. The effectiveness of treatment of patients with burning mouth syndrome can be significantly increased by using biofeedback-based therapy [11]. This method allows maintaining a high level of psychosocial functioning of patients even if painful symptoms are not completely reduced [20]. Electroencephalographic biofeedback (neurobiofeedback) is considered the most promising in this regard [10].

Improving the psychological state of patients and reducing anxiety levels detected in long-term treatment courses using neurobiofeedback is accompanied by normalization of the activity of endogenous opioid systems under stressful conditions, which also affects pain perception [16].

Cognitive psychotherapy has been successfully used in the treatment of chronic pain disorders. The therapy process is aimed at strengthening the patient's belief in recovery and improving his mood, which is essential for mobilizing internal forces to cope with the disease, changing attitudes towards his condition and the environment [18, 3]. Cognitive behavioral psychotherapy has shown high effectiveness in the treatment of somatoform disorders (somatoform pain disorder) compared to other approaches in terms of reducing pain intensity and the number of complaints [3].

Discussion: Cognitive psychotherapy has been shown to be effective for burning mouth syndrome [4]. A controlled study [7] has shown that cognitive psychotherapy, in addition to reducing emotional distress, reduces pain intensity and consequently improves quality of life. Increased compliance and avoidance of overuse of analgesics are particular benefits of psychotherapy. A ten-week course of cognitive-behavioral psychotherapy reduced the catastrophic perception of chronic pain and reduced negative reactions to painful episodes [20]. The duration of treatment has been reported to be an important factor to consider when adding cognitive psychotherapy to the treatment of chronic pain [35].

Cognitive therapy strategies have been successfully used in the treatment of comorbid pathology that combines pain and negative emotions [20]. Cognitive models of emotional disorders and chronic pain disorders are being developed. The work of researchers is aimed at developing the main cognitive-behavioral principles of the treatment of chronic pain based on cognitive psychotherapy and developing clinical recommendations for the integration of cognitive psychotherapy into the complex treatment of oral cavity syndrome [18]. Given the confirmation of the negative interaction between oral cavity syndrome and negative emotions, and taking into account the negative impact of depression on the treatment of chronic pain, the appointment of cognitive psychotherapy is considered quite justified [20].

Conclusion: During psychotherapy, it is important to convey to the patient's mind the role of emotions in the experience of pain and the possibility of emotional disorders transforming into a pain syndrome. Patients with burning mouth syndrome should be informed about the ongoing treatment and the dynamics of the oral cavity [4]. When conducting psychotherapy, it is necessary to discuss the issues of dealing with fear, assertive behavior strategies, and avoiding confrontation. It is necessary to help the patient recognize the presence of dysfunctional beliefs, challenge them, and form new, more constructive ones. This leads to gradual changes in the patient's behavior and a decrease in negative experiences [15].

A meta-analysis comparing the outcomes of cognitive-behavioral and pharmacological treatments for burning mouth syndrome found similar levels of efficacy [53]. However, despite the many medications and psychotherapeutic approaches used to treat burning mouth syndrome, its efficacy remains low, prompting the search for new therapeutic strategies that can help improve treatment outcomes;

List of used literature:

1. Iyer V. Psychology in dental practice. – SPb: Peter, 2008. – 224 p.
2. Aleksandrovsky Yu.A. Borderline mental disorders: a guide for doctors. – 4th ed., revised. And add. – M.: GEOTAR-Media, 2007. – 720 p.
3. Bardenstein LM, Klimov AB, Panin MG, Mikhailova VV The effectiveness of drug correction of psychopathological conditions in patients with maxillofacial deformities // Problems of neurostomatology and dentistry. – 1998.– No. 1.– P. 52–56.
4. Borisova EG Organization of medical care for patients with neurodental diseases in outpatient settings / EG Borisova // Dentistry. – 1995. – No. 5. – p. 68.
5. Grishina NV, Puzin MN, Gerasimenko M.Yu., Turbina LG The use of electrosleep in the treatment of burning mouth syndrome. // Problems of neurostomy. – 1999. – No. 4. – P. 28 – 32.
6. Dychko EN Neurogenic aspects of the pathogenesis of glossalgia / EN Dychko, VN Mirtovskaya // Dentistry. - 1990. - No. 6. - pp. 38-39.

7. Zoyirov T. E. et al. PROCESSES AND THEIR COMPLICATIONS IN THE FACE-JAW AREA AND ORAL MUCOSA OF PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM KOVID-19 INFECTION //SUSTAINABILITY OF EDUCATION, SOCIO-ECONOMIC SCIENCE THEORY. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 17-19.
8. Kaxxorovna R. B. et al. IMPROVEMENT OF THERAPEUTIC MEASURES FOR CHANGES IN THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE ORAL CAVITY AND TONGUE OF THE PATIENT IN THE POSTOPERATIVE BARIATRIC STATE //International Journal of Medical Sciences And Clinical Research. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 01. – С. 31-36.
9. Raxmonova B., Muxammadkulov V. IMPROVING THERAPEUTIC MEASURES FOR CHANGES IN THE ORAL MUCOSA AND TONGUE OF THE PATIENT IN A POSTOPERATIVE BARIATRIC CONDITION //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 576-579.
10. Kaxharovna R. B. et al. YUZ VA JAGDA ZAMONAVIY ENDOSKOPIK JARROHLIKNING YUTUQ VA KAMCHILIKLARI //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 72-76.
11. Ибрагимов Д. Д., Гаффаров У. Б., Рахмонова Б. К. КОВИД-19 ИНФЕКЦИЯСИ БИЛАН ОГРИГАН БЕМОРЛАРНИНГ ЮЗ-ЖАГ СОХАСИДА ВА ОГИЗ БУШЛИГИ ШИЛЛИК КАВАТЛАРИДА КЕЧАДИГАН ЖАРАЁНЛАР ВА УЛАРНИНГ //Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 25. – С. 107-109.
12. Raxmonova B., Xaydarova D., Sadikova S. TREATMENT OF FRACTURES OF THE UPPER AND LOWER HEAD IN ELDERLY PATIENTS USING THE IMMOBILIZATION METHOD IMPACT ON PERIODONTAL TISSUE //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D10. – С. 194-198.
13. Kakhhorovna R. B. et al. IMPROVING THE SURGICAL METHOD OF SCAR MICROSTOMY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2023. – Т. 11. – №. 9. – С. 300-304.
14. Kakharovna R. B., Mekhrojiddinovich B. X. MODERN ENDOSCOPIC SURGERY ON THE FACE AND JAW ACHIEVEMENTS AND DISADVANTAGES //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 17. – С. 136-141.
15. Kakhkhorovna R. B. CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE DISSEMINATED PERIODONTITIS IN INFECTED PATIENTS Entry. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education //Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – Т. 11. – №. 4. – С. 2095-2103.
16. Рахманова Б. К. и др. ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И НЕДОСТАТКИ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЭНДОСКОПИЧЕСКОЙ ХИРУРГИИ ЛИЦА И ЧЕЛЮСТИ //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 17. – С. 129-. 135.